

MICROMECHANICAL MODELING OF CROSS-PLY TITANIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH SILICON-CARBIDE FIBRES

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SUMMARY: A three-dimensional, double-layer unit cell model is used to predict the overall stress/strain behaviour and damage of a $[0/90]_{ns}$ SCS-6 fibre/titanium matrix cross-ply laminate. The titanium matrix is represented by a rate-dependent elastic-plastic constitutive model, recently developed, which has been incorporated into finite element code ADINA, as user-defined material model. A criterion of the initiation of damage and post-damage constitutive relation is introduced for the interfacial elements between the fiber and matrix. The finite element analysis results are compared with the experimental data, and it is found that the model prediction of the rate-dependent stress-strain response is in good agreement with the experiment data. The success of the micromechanical analysis can be attributed to the accurate representation of the matrix property by the constitutive model and the correct simulation of the damage mechanism.

KEYWORDS: micromechanics, fibre-reinforced composites, constitutive model, finite element analysis, interfacial damage, titanium matrix.

INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced titanium matrix composites are engineered materials with potential applications in severe thermomechanical loading conditions and where lightweight, high stiffness and strength are required. For the designers, it is a vital importance to have reliable analysis tools, which can be used to predict mechanical properties and damage mechanisms of this new generation of composite materials. Micro-mechanical models have been used in study the properties and damage of composite materials. In this methodology, a representative volume element (RVE) or unit cell, consisting of two constituents (fibre and matrix) is analysed. Based on the known properties of the fibre and matrix material, the global behaviour of the composites is then predicted. It is obvious that an essential part of this methodology is the requirement of an accurate constitutive model for each constituent. For the silicon-carbide fibers, a linear elastic model (Hookes' Law) usually suffices. However, the titanium matrix is a highly rate- and temperature-dependent elastic/plastic material with much more complex behaviour, therefore, a more sophisticated constitutive model is required. Considerable research effort has been devoted

to develop appropriate constitutive models for the titanium alloys, among them, a type of so-called unified viscoplastic models [1-2].

Experimental studies have shown that the most significant damage mechanism of the SiC/Ti composites when subjected to transverse tensile loading, is the fiber/matrix interfacial debonding [3]. This damage could happen at relatively low level of loading, and will consequently, affect the global response of the composite. Different interface failure criteria as well as different strategies to model the debonding effect have been suggested [4-5]. Another important feature to be considered is the residual stress introduced in the material processing stage. The matrix has a larger coefficient of thermal expansion than that of the fibre. Tensile residual stresses both in the axial and circumferential directions in the matrix could build up due to the cooling from the processing temperature. Therefore, the above two mechanisms must be combined into a micromechanical model in order to obtain realistic results.

In this paper, a micromechanical finite element analysis is carried out for a $[0/90]_{ns}$ SCS-6 fibre/titanium matrix cross-ply laminate. The RVE consists of two cubes containing two fibres in perpendicular directions. To represent accurately the titanium matrix properties, a rate-dependent elastic-plastic constitutive model developed by the first two authors is presented first. To simulate the interfacial debonding, a very thin-layer of interfacial elements is introduced around each fibre. A maximum normal traction criterion is used as a failure criterion for the interface element. Before the failure, the interface elements are assumed to have the same property as the fibre. After the failure, a special constitutive relation is applied such that the stress vector drops to zero in short time duration. In addition, the initial residual stress effect is also included. The above rate-dependent elastic-plastic constitutive model and the failure model have been combined into a finite element analysis code ADINA, as user-defined material models. The predicted global rate-dependent stress-strain responses will be compared to the experimental data.

RATE-DEPENDENT ELASTIC-PLASTIC CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

In this model, two types of surfaces are defined in the stress space, viz: yield surface and stress memory surface. The rate-dependent von Mises yield surface is represented by:

$$\phi_y = \frac{3}{2} \bar{s}_{ij} \bar{s}_{ij} - q^2 (\dot{\epsilon}_{eq}, l_p) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{s}_{ij} = \bar{\sigma}_{ij} - \delta_{ij} \bar{\sigma}_{kk} / 3$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = \sigma_{ij} - \alpha_{ij}$. The α_{ij} and q specify the center and radius of the yield surface. Three rate-dependent uniaxial stress-strain curves of the titanium matrix at 650°C [2] are shown in Fig. 1. A characteristic feature of this type of response is an increase of the initial yield stress with increasing strain-rate. Incorporate the conventional logarithmic strain-rate dependence, the radius q can be expressed as,

$$q = q[\log(\dot{\epsilon}_{eq} / \dot{\epsilon}_{eq}^0), l_p] \quad (2)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}_{eq}$ is the current von Mises equivalent strain-rate, $\dot{\epsilon}_{eq}^0$ is a reference equivalent strain-rate and is usually taken to be the slowest strain rate in the studied range. The parameter l_p is the accumulated plastic strain, which is used to describe cyclic hardening or softening behaviour of

materials. For the current titanium matrix, this effect is neglected. More detailed description regarding the influence of l_p can be found in [7].

Fig. 1 Rate-dependent uniaxial stress-strain curves of titanium matrix at 650°C

The stress memory surface is related to the maximum equivalent stress level ($\sigma_{eq} = \sqrt{3s_{ij}s_{ij}/2}$) experienced in the previous loading history:

$$\phi_m = \frac{3}{2}s_{ij}s_{ij} - R^2(\sigma_{eq,max}) = 0 \quad (3)$$

Based on the conventional assumption that total strain-rate can be decomposed into elastic and plastic parts, the rate form stress-strain relation can be expressed as

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = \frac{E}{1+\nu} \left\{ \delta_{ik}\delta_{jl} + \frac{\nu}{1-2\nu} \delta_{ij}\delta_{kl} - \frac{9g\bar{s}_{ij}\bar{s}_{kl}}{[(1+\nu)/E] + 9\bar{s}_{mn}\bar{s}_{mn}} \right\} \dot{\epsilon}_{kl}, \quad (4)$$

and

$$g = \frac{1}{4q^2} \left(\frac{1}{E_t} - \frac{1}{E} \right) \quad (5)$$

where E_t is the current tangent modulus.

Depending on the relative position of the current stress point with respect to the yield and the stress memory surfaces, three types of loading cases are distinguished, i.e. elastic loading, monotonic plastic and plastic reloading. If the stress point is inside the yield surface or there is elastic unloading, then $s_{ij}\dot{\sigma}_{ij} < 0$, and this is termed elastic loading case. For the plastic loading, $s_{ij}\dot{\sigma}_{ij} > 0$, and the current stress point is on the yield surface. However, if the maximum equivalent stress increases with the plastic loading, then the stress memory surface will expand but it will remain tangent to the yield surface, and this type of loading is defined as the monotonic plastic loading case. The plastic loading, in which the current stress point is inside the stress memory surface, is classified as the plastic reloading case. For this case, the stress memory surface does not change. Whenever there is a transition from the elastic loading to the plastic

loading, the size of the yield surface would depend on the current equivalent strain-rate, eqn 2. For the latter two plastic loading cases, the evolution rules of the yield and the calculation of the tangent modulus, E_t in eqn 5, are different.

For the monotonic plastic loading, the evolution rule of the centre of the yield surface, α_{ij} is determined from,

$$\dot{\alpha}_{ij} = \dot{\mu}(\sigma_{ij}^{\text{lim}} - \sigma_{ij}^y) \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{ij}^{\text{lim}} = \frac{R_{\text{lim}}}{q}(\sigma_{ij}^y - \alpha_{ij}) \quad (6)$$

where σ_{ij}^y is the current stress point, which is on the yield surface, R_{lim} is a constant. Note that when $R_{\text{lim}} \gg q$, the conventional Ziegler's rule is recovered. The value of E_t is calculated based on the current equivalent stress value and the rate-dependent stress-strain curves.

For the plastic reloading case, the evolution rule of the centre α_{ij} of the yield surface is expressed as,

$$\dot{\alpha}_{ij} = \dot{\mu}(\sigma_{ij}^m - \sigma_{ij}^y). \quad (7)$$

where σ_{ij}^m is a point on the stress memory surface whose exterior normal is parallel to the outward normal of current stress point σ_{ij}^y . The calculation of E_t requires attention, it is related to the ratio of two distances related to three stress points: σ_{ij}^y , σ_{ij}^m and the stress point at which the plastic reloading took place. Due to the space limitation this will not be explained here, the reader is encouraged to consult refs [6-7].

This rate-dependent constitutive model has been incorporated into the ADINA code through the user-defined material subroutine in order to perform finite element analysis. The required input material data were obtained from the uniaxial stress-strain curves of the titanium matrix at three different orders of strain-rates shown in Fig. 1. In the calculation, the reference strain-rate was taken to be 8.3×10^{-6} . The q and E_t values for any strain-rate lower than 8.3×10^{-6} were assumed to be the same as that of this rate. The predicted rate-dependent stress-strain curves by the program (only one matrix element was used) are also shown in Fig. 1.

RVE MODEL FOR [0/90]_{ns} CROSS-PLY LAMINATE

It is assumed that fibres are uniformly distributed in the matrix and have the same radii, therefore, the micromechanical model of the [0/90]_{ns} cross-ply can be represented by two cubes containing two fibres in perpendicular directions. Only global uniaxial loading is considered in this paper. Due to the symmetry of geometry and loading condition, only 1/8 of the model needs to be considered. The model with the finite element mesh is shown in Fig. 2. Symmetric boundary conditions (zero normal displacements) are applied to the three symmetric surfaces. To other three surfaces, the periodicity condition will be applied; i.e. a plane remains plane but is allowed to displace in the normal direction. Note that a thin layer of interfacial elements is

introduced around each fibre for the treatment of interfacial debonding, which will be discussed in the next section.

Fig. 2 RVE model for $[0/90]_{ns}$ cross ply laminate with FEM mesh

CONSTITUTIVE RELATION FOR INTERFACIAL ELEMENTS

As mentioned in the introduction, the dominant damage mechanism in the SiC/Titanium cross plies is the interface debonding. To consider this effect, a thin layer of interfacial elements was introduced around each fibre in the RVE model, see Fig. 2. For this group of elements, a damage criterion, i.e. the maximum traction normal to the interface, is introduced. Once the normal traction (tensile) in an element (in a Gauss integration point) reaches a critical value, $T_n \geq T_c$, the element is considered to undergo damage and cannot carry any load, i.e. the stress vector must be zero. Because the interface can carry a compressive pressure even when “damaged”, a recovery criterion is also established for the interface elements. That is, after the initiation of damage, with the change of loading conditions, if the normal strain becomes negative, the stiffness of the element will be recovered. Prior to the damage initiation, the element property can either be the same as the matrix or the fibre. (The volume fraction will not change much because the interface layer is very thin.) For the simplicity, it is assumed that the interface elements have the same elastic property as the fibre before the damage, i.e. the constitutive relation is described by:

$$\{\dot{\sigma}\} = E[A]^{-1}\{\dot{\epsilon}\}, \quad (8)$$

where $[A]$ is a matrix related to the Poisson ratio. After the damage, however, the following constitutive relation is used,

$$\{\dot{\sigma}\} = \beta E[A]^{-1}\{\dot{\epsilon}\} - a\{\sigma\}, \quad (9)$$

where β is a small number ($<10^{-4}$) and a is a constant. With a proper choice of the value of a , the above constitutive relation would reduce the stress vector to very small value in a short time (zero is the asymptotic limit). Thus, the debonding process is simulated in accordance with the

above description. Figure 3 shows the response of the interface element after introducing the damage criterion.

Fig. 3 Response of the interfacial elements before and after damage

RESULTS OF FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The responses of the $[0/90]_{ns}$ SiC/Titanium laminate under two different constant stress-rates (10.26 MPa/s and 1026 MPa/s) are determined. The material constants used in the calculation are:

For SiC fiber (Isotropic elastic material):

$$E=370\,000\text{ MPa}, \nu=0.25, \alpha=3.826 \times 10^{-6}\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1};$$

For interfacial elements:

$$E=370\,000\text{ MPa}, \nu=0.25, \alpha=3.826 \times 10^{-6}\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}, T_C=103\text{ MPa}, \beta=10^{-5}\text{ and } a=0.02\text{ s}^{-1};$$

For titanium matrix:

$$E=86600\text{ MPa}, \nu=0.34, \alpha=8.83 \times 10^{-6}\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}, R_{lim}=4600\text{ MPa},$$

$$q(\dot{\epsilon}_{eq}) = 46.43 \left\{ 1 + 0.3292 \left[\log \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_{eq}}{\dot{\epsilon}_{eq}^0} \right) \right]^{2.99} \right\} \text{ and } \dot{\epsilon}_{eq}^0 = 8.3 \times 10^{-6}\text{ s}^{-1}$$

Thermal stresses are first obtained by assuming a cooling from the consolidation temperature of 900°C to the hold temperature 650°C . Figure 4 shows the distribution of the residual stresses in the RVE (σ_{yy} , along the 0 fibre vertical direction). It can be seen that the matrix is subjected to a tensile stress state while the fibres are under a compressive stress both in hoop and axial directions.

Fig. 4 Distribution of thermal residual stress σ_{yy} in the RVE mode I

The external traction load is subsequently applied to the RVE. It is to be noted that although the global applied stress-rate is constant, the stress or strain-rates at different elements vary with time and are no longer constant due to the non-uniform distribution of the stresses and strains in the RVE. For the sake of comparison, both the FEM predictions with and without inclusion of interfacial damage are presented in Fig. 5. It can be seen that the predictions without interface damage are good only at a low level of load (about 100MPa). Beyond this level they (dashed lines) deviate appreciably from the experimental data. However, the FEM predictions, which incorporate a debonding criterion and damage progressing process (solid lines), are in good agreement with the experimental data in the full loading range as well as in the unloading part.

Fig. 5 Predicted stress-strain response of $[0/90]_{ns}$ cross-ply under two different constant stress-rates loading

The application of the micro-mechanical analysis is not only limited to obtaining the global stress-strain behaviour. It is also very useful in study of the damage mechanisms of the fibre-reinforced composite laminates. The macromechanical approaches (classical laminate theory, etc.) homogenize the properties of each lamina in a laminate and thus can only predict an averaged stress/strain state in each lamina. The advantage of the current micromechanical method over the macro-modeling is that it provides a detailed local stress/strain distribution in each lamina and between the neighboring laminae. It is the local stress/strain characteristics, which dominate the damage initiation. And with the damage propagation, further redistribution of the stress/strain state in the composites takes place. By the introduction of a proper damage criterion, a global perspective of the damage process, i.e. the initiation and propagation of the interfacial debonding can be obtained. Figure 6 shows the development of the interfacial debonding in the laminate for $\dot{\sigma} = 10.26 \text{MPa/s}$. At a global applied stress of 91 MPa, damage initiates in the interface of 90° fiber (Note the threshold value $T_C = 103 \text{MPa}$). With the increasing load the debonding propagates around the fibre relatively fast at the beginning but slows down later and stops at the last two rows of the interfacial elements where the normal stress is always compressive.

Fig. 6 Development of interfacial debonding with the increasing applied load

CONCLUSIONS

A micromechanical modeling approach combined with finite element analysis has been successfully applied to a $[0/90]_{ns}$ SCS-6 fibre/titanium matrix cross-ply laminate. Not only the global rate-dependent stress-strain response of the laminate but also the damage initiation and propagation process has been predicted. The success of the model prediction can be attributed to the following two important ingredients involved in the micromechanical analysis:

1. The proposed rate-dependent elastic-plastic constitutive model is capable of properly representing the titanium matrix properties. The model is relatively simple and easy to apply. The material constants or functions are determined based on the uniaxial test data.
2. The dominant damage mode of the $[0/90]_{ns}$ SCS-6 fibre /titanium matrix cross-ply laminate (interfacial debonding) has been properly simulated. It is through the introduction of the failure criterion and the implementation of the post-damage stress/strain relation, that the stiffness and the stress of the interfacial elements decreases to a very small value at short time interval.

The rate-dependent constitutive model described herein can be applied to other types of matrices undergoing elastic-plastic deformation. The strategy of the numerical implementation of damage process can also be used in the simulation of various damage mechanisms (interface debonding, matrix damage, etc.) of other fiber reinforced composite laminates. Through such a micromechanical analysis, a better understanding of the characteristics of the local stress/strain distribution in the composite laminates can be obtained.

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